

This is the time set, which goes as followed:

- The root, 0th time paired 0th time, the extra 0th time, and the outcome of another 0th time.
- The moment, 1 time paired 1 time, the extra 1st time, and the outcome of another 1st time.
- The second, 2 time paired 2 time, the extra 2nd time, and the outcome of another 2nd time.
- The minute, 3 time paired 3 time, the extra 3rd time, and the outcome of another 3rd time.
- The hour, 4th time paired 4th time, the extra 4th time, and the outcome of another 4th time.
- The gap, 5th time paired 5th time, the extra 5th time, and the outcome of another 5th time.
- The cycle, 6th time paired 6th time, the extra 6th time, and the outcome of another 6th time.
- The day, 7 time paired 7 time, the extra 7th time, and the outcome of another 7th time.

Set.